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Atrial fibrillation and cognitive decline among patients with Alzheimer's disease, vascular and mixed dementia

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Abstract

Background. Atrial fibrillation (AF) and dementia often coexist in elderly. It is supposed that patients with AF have higher risk for development of incident dementia. The aim of our study was to examine the impact of AF on cognitive functions and cognitive decline of patients with Alzheimer's disease (AD), vascular cognitive impairment (VCI) and mixed (vascular and Alzheimer's) dementia (MxD).

Material and methods: We examined 146 patients with cognitive impairment (76.71 ± 7.47 year-old, 48 males and 98 females; 38 with AD, 56 with VCI and 52 with MxD; 37 with and 109 without AF). All patients were examined twice (in interval of 2 years) with the following neuropsychological battery: Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE), 10 Words Memory Test, 5min - delayed recall (DR) and Word Recognition Test (WRT)), Isaac Set Test (IST), Literal Fluency Test (LFT), 90-sec.-Digit Symbol Substitution Test, Digit Span Test (DST) forward and backward and Clock Drawing Test (CDT). All results were interpreted for $p < 0.05$.

Results: In total, patients with AF showed more pronounced decrease in IST performance. Among AD group, patients with AF had more severe decline in executive functioning. Among patients with VCI, patients with AF showed more severe decline in MMSE, IST, LFT, STM, DR and CDT. We failed to find any cognitive differences between patients with and without AF in MxD group.

Conclusions: The study highlights the importance of AF for cognitive functioning of patients with the most common dementias worldwide. The early

detection of AF and its early treatment might have positive effect on cognition of such patients and especially in cases with VCI and AD.

Background:

Atrial fibrillation (AF) and dementia often coexist in elderly (Fekete, 2025). It is supposed that patients with AF have higher risk for incident dementia (incl. vascular and Alzheimer's dementia), although the exact mechanisms of its impact remain unclear (Nakase, 2023; Du, 2026). Moreover, some studies show that anticoagulant treatment has protective effect on cognition of patients with AF, although even with treatment such patients have higher risk for cognitive impairment (Du, 2026). Despite this, the anticoagulant treatment carries some specific risk in cases with dementia, such as non-compliance, polypharmacy, higher risk for bleeding (incl. brain hemorrhages), particularly in cases with frequent falls (Mitchell, 2023).

It is unclear, whether AF can lead to additional cognitive decline in cases with already developed dementia.

The aim of our study was to examine the impact of AF on cognitive functions and cognitive decline of patients with Alzheimer's disease (AD), vascular cognitive impairment (VCI) and mixed (vascular and Alzheimer's) dementia (MxD).

Material and methods:

We examined 146 patients with cognitive impairment (76.71 ± 7.47 year-old, 48 males and 98 females; 38 with AD, 56 with VCI and 52 with MxD). The inclusion criteria for the study were: 1. Age ≥ 60 years; 2. Confirmed by neuropsychologist cognitive impairment at ≥ 2 cognitive domains; 3. Confirmed on the basis of history, neurological and somatic examination, laboratory data and imaging study diagnosis of AD or VCI or MxD; 4. Lack of other neurological diseases such as trauma, brain tumors, neuro-infections, demyelinating diseases or epilepsy; 5. Lack of decompensation of coexisted somatic diseases during the study; 6. Lack

of psychiatric diseases, except of mild depression or anxiety; 7. Lack of treatment or usage of benzodiazepines, modafinile acetate, hallucinogens and other psychoactive drugs, except for low dosages of Quetiapine ($\leq 50\text{mg/d}$), Pregabalin ($\leq 150\text{mg/d}$), Gabapentin ($\leq 600\text{mg/d}$), or antidepressants; 8. Lack of alcohol abuse or usage of forbidden substances; 9. Signed written informed consent. After the recruitment, all patients were examined with 24 hour Holter- Electrocardiography (Holter ECG) and divided into two groups – with and without AF.

All patients were examined via the following neuropsychological battery: Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE), 10 Words Memory Test (for short term memory (STM) – average from 5 trials; 5min - delayed recall (DR) and Word Recognition Test (WRT)), Isaacs Set Test (IST) for verbal fluency, Literal Fluency Test (LFT), 90-sec.-Digit Symbol Substitution Test (DSST), Digit Span Test (DST) forward and backward for attention and Clock Drawing Test (CDT). They were examined again 2 years after the first examination with the same neuropsychological battery. All patients with AF were treated with oral anticoagulants.

The statistical analysis was done via descriptive analysis, t-test and paired t-test (for normal value distribution) or non-parametric tests (Mann-Whitney/Wilcoxon and Kruskal Wallis) by “Statgraphics 20 Plus” and SPSS 20. All results were interpreted at a 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$).

Results:

The demographic characteristics of our sample are given at table 1. The majority of our patients were elderly. Female gender prevailed over male. Most of them were with middle formal education. Patients with and without AF had similar demographic characteristics and they could be compared.

Differences in total sample:

In total, patients with AF showed more pronounced decrease in IST performance (-5 vs -2, $p=0.0220$) and LFT (-2 vs -4, $p=0.0154$) than those without. We failed to find any other intergroup differences among patients in total sample.

Patients with AD: Among AD group, patients with AF had more severe decline in IST, LFT, CDT, DST forward and backward performances (see table 2), although no association between AF and decline in MMSE, DSST and verbal memory test was found.

Patients with VCI. Among patients with VCI, patients with AF showed more severe decline in MMSE, IST, LFT, STM, DR and CDT (see table 3).

Patients with MxD. We failed to find any differences in cognitive functions between patients with and without AF.

Discussion:

AF and dementia frequently coexist and AF plays important role for the development of dementia. However, it is supposed that even in cases with adequate anticoagulation, patients with AF show more pronounced cognitive decline, non-associated with thrombotic incidents (Tribhuvan, 2026). Our patients with AF in general sample show only faster decline in information processing speed that indicate increased executive dysfunction among such patients.

Among our patients with AD we also find faster executive function decline but in more executive domains, including information processing speed, working memory and attention. Nakase et al. (2023) also found that patients with AD and AF had significantly lower MMSE scores than those with AD alone. They proposed that the white matter lesions but not the impairment of cerebral blood flow play important role for cognitive decline in AD (Nakase, 2023).

Patients with VCI and AF show additional decline not only in executive functions, but also they show memory decline (STM and DR) and special abilities than those without. Neuroimaging studies in such cases revealed increased frequency of

strokes, lacunar strokes, white matter hyperintensities, cerebral microbleeds and cortical atrophy, probably associated with disconnection (Fekete, 2025). Early detection and treatment of AF might have positive effect on cognition and quality of life in cases with VCI.

However, we failed to find any differences between patients with and without AF among MxD. Such finding surprises us, although in this group AF is most common. However, all patients with MxD have other vascular risk factors and cortical atrophy and white matter changes. Such patients also have principally lower cognitive functioning than those with VCI. Thus, AF may play the same role as the complex of other vascular risk factors, that play role as obscuring factors. We think that other wider and profound studies should be done on this question.

Conclusions: The study highlights the importance of AF for cognitive functioning of patients with the most common dementias worldwide. The early detection of AF and its early treatment might have positive effect on cognition of such patients and especially in cases with VCI and AD.

Limitations of the study: Our study samples were relatively small. Moreover, the examined period of time (interval of the study) was relatively short. However, the study highlights the importance of AF for cognitive decline in cases with dementia.

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Tables:

Table 1 Demographic data

	Without AF	With AF	Total
AD	30	8	38
VCI	43	13	56
MxD	36	16	52
Total	109 (73%)	37 (27%)	149 (100%)
			P
Age (years)	76.53±7.43	77.22±7.67	p>0,05
Male:Female ratio	37:72	11:26	p>0.05
Formal education	10:57:42	2:26:9	p>0.05

(Basic:Middle:High)			
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Table 2. The association between AF and cognitive decline among patients with AD

The association between AF (x) and	p=
IST1 (p.)	>0.05
IST2 (p.)	>0.05
Decline on IST performance (p.)	0.0151
LFT 1 (p.)	>0.05
LFT 2 (p.)	0.0470
Decline on IST performance (p.)	0.0296
CDT 1 (number of errors)	0.0152
CDT 2 (number of errors)	0.0491
Increase of errors on CDT	0.0458
DST forward 1 (p.)	>0.05
DST backward 2 (p.)	0.0333
Decline on DST forward performance (p.)	0.0085
DST backward 1 (p.)	0.0311
DST backward 2 (p.)	0.0309
Decline on DST backward performance (p.)	0.0405

Table 3. Associations between AF and cognitive decline among patients with VCI.

Association between AF (x) and	p=
MMSE 1 (p.)	>0.05
MMSE 2 (p.)	0.0479
Decline on MMSE performance (p.)	0.0371
IST1 (p.)	p>0.05
IST2 (p.)	p>0.05
Decline on IST (p.)	0.0165
LFT 1 (p.)	p>0.05
LFT 2 (p.)	p>0.05
Decline on LFT (p.)	0.0432
STM 1 (words)	p>0.05
STM 2 (words)	0.0435
Decline on STM (words)	0.02578
DR 1 (words)	0.0443
DR 2 (words)	0.0183
Decline on DR (words)	0.0198
CDT 1 (errors)	>0.05

CDT 2 (errors)	0.0160
Decline on CDT (errors)	0.0312